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**THE REPRESENTATION OF XENOPHOBIA AND THE FOREIGN “OTHER” IN
BRAM STOKER’S DRACULA**

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Annotation: *This paper investigates the representation of xenophobia and the construction of the foreign “other” in Bram Stoker’s Dracula, describing broader social and racial anxieties of English Empire during the Victorian period. The subject of the article remains relevant due to contemporary disputes about immigration, national and cultural identities, and ethnic minorities that continue to reflect the fears of 19th century England. Literature of the Victorian period presents significant details, which help discover the roots of xenophobia in history and track its development. The methodology of the the analysis lies in close reading of Dracula by Bram Stoker intertwining the main theme of the book with postcolonial theory and Victorian history and culture. Key references that served as a support of the study are Edwards Said’s Orientalism, Stephen Arata’s concept of reverse colonization and Max Nordau’s book “Degeneration”, that talks about decay of western civilizations. The article presents the Dracula as a figure of cultural and national anxiety and symbolizes Eastern Europe as something primitive and threatening the civilized society of England. The analysis of the book shows the narrative form of the novel, its gender roles and the union of British western men which tries to take over the threatening east, thus, reinforcing xenophobia.*

Keywords: *Victorian period, gothic literature, xenophobia, British Empire, colonization, orientalism, Dracula, Eastern Europe, immigration, fears.*

Dracula was written by Irish writer Bram Stoker and published in 1897. It is considered one of the most influential Gothic works in English literature. The novel is well-known for its gothic horror elements such as vampires, battle between good and evil and supernatural powers and events, but it also implied social and political fears of The Victorian era. One of the main and crucial of these fears is the anxiety about foreigners and their influence on society, which is called xenophobia in a scientific way.

The foreign “other” in Dracula is expressed by the Count Dracula who lives in Eastern Europe in Transylvania and travels to London to spread his influence. Judging from the perspective of Victorian society, Dracula was not just a monster, but a foreigner who threatened to corrupt English society. Even though the novel positions itself as a horror story, it can be easily read as a novel describing cultural and imperial fears and anxieties about immigration, race and national identity.

In order to have a better understanding of xenophobia in Dracula, it is important to know the historical context of the time when Dracula was written. In the 90th years of the 19th century Britain was filled with anxieties. Colonial wars in Africa and Asia were proving costly and, at times humiliating. Domestic social problems like poverty, crime, disease and overcrowding in major cities were worsening. The great British Empire began to slowly decrease in her powerfulness leading to concern about the degeneration of the British nation. The concept of degeneration was deeply influential in the 1880s and 1890s. Shaped by evolutionary theory of Charles Darwin, degeneration theory claimed that just as species could evolve upward toward greater complexity, they could also devolve or regress downward toward more primitive states. Applied to human beings, this idea produced enormous anxiety.

According to Max Nordau and his book “Degeneration”, modernity was causing physical and moral decay in Western regions, especially British empire [1]. Meanwhile immigration in England was upswinging and immigrants such as Jews, Russians and Poles started to fill in the Empire. The

anxiety about immigrations was spreading so fast that Parliament of the United Kingdom in 1905 presented a law called Aliens Act that was aimed to control the immigration. The vampire fiction, especially of the 19th century, as Jules Zanger argues, often hides contemporary anxiety about immigration of the Jews, who comes from East and influences the society in negative way. [2]

The parallels between Dracula and anti-Semitic tropes are striking and have been noted by numerous scholars. Dracula is obsessed with blood, he is associated with financial affairs, operates in secret and exploits the trust of his hosts. The novel also presented the growing anxiety of Britain's invasion by the foreign "other". The 1890s saw a wave of "invasion literature" in Britain, in which novels and stories imagined foreign powers successfully invading and conquering Britain. The most famous example is H. G. Wells's *The War of the Worlds*, published in 1898, a year after *Dracula*, in which invaders from Mars lay waste to the English countryside. Dracula belongs to this broader cultural moment, but displaces the fear of invasion onto a supernatural, racially coded figure from the semi-oriental East.

Stephen D. Arata in her essay "The occidental Tourist: Dracula and the anxiety of reverse colonization" claims that "Dracula" shows fears of reverse colonization, which means that all the people and nations which Britain was dominating and colonizing, one day will return the favor and colonize Britain. In *Dracula* we can see the exact fear become the reality where the colonized oppresses the colonizer. [3]

From the beginning of the novel, Bram Stoker pays a lot of attention to describing the difference in racial appearance of Count Dracula. The narration starts with Jonathan Harker's diary entry where he describes his journey to Transylvania where he admires the beauty of the nation. However, with time passing he sees threats in the people who live there, and everything from customs to landscapes becomes alien. When he meets Dracula, Jonathan starts to describe his physique and looks, emphasizing his foreignness. He describes his face as "strong with high bridge of the thin nose...his eyebrows were very massive with bushy hair that seemed to curl in its own profusion..." [4]

Such description refers to the common stereotype of appearance that is typical for the East European nation. Dracula's big nose, heavy eyebrows and pale skin mark him as a figure of something strange and other. In nineteenth century literature, it was common to depict racial anxiety through the hideous, almost monster-like appearance, using it as a symbol of inferiority. Dracula's racial otherness is not fixed in a single category. Many scholars have identified him with different racial groups such as Eastern European, Jews, Romani people or a generalized image of Orientals. Dracula is not simply a representation of certain racial group like Jews or Oriental, he is all of this threatening types at once. He is a full weight of Victorian xenophobia in a single body.

Dracula's country of origin, Transylvania, is portrayed as a primitive and uncivilized world, full of peasants. Jonathan describes it as wild and superstitious, where citizens always cross themselves and give Jonathan garlic and crucifixes to prevent vampires' attacks. In accordance with Edward Said and his "Orientalism", such stereotypes where East is irrational and threatening are created to contrast the progressive West and make it seem more civilized and dominant. [5]

The strongest example of xenophobia in Bram Stoker's *Dracula* is the Count's planned and purposeful journey to London, England. Dracula is presented as an active, intelligent and cunning agent who intends to buy property in England and thoroughly calculated his invasion. When Dracula tells Jonathan "I long to go through the crowded streets of your mighty London, to be the midst of the whirl and rush of humanity" he is expressing the colonial desire. He wants to be in the center of England and spread his authority there. [4]

Another important moment that represents xenophobia in the novel is when Dracula arrives to England on the ship *Demeter* after a trip where the entire crew gets killed. This scene shows that the East brings death and disease to the civilization. Anne Mcwhir notes that Dracula spreads his vampirism through contagion, like bites and interaction with blood. It serves as a metaphor of infection, which was also one of the main fears of British society of that time, such as syphilis, tuberculosis and cholera. [6]

The foreign “other” in *Dracula* has a strong connection to fears about female sexuality and gender roles, because Dracula’s main victims are women: Lucy Westenra and Mina Harker. He attacks them in an intimate, almost sexual way, and it leads us to another Victorian fear, which is the corruption of white women by foreigners. Lucy Westenra’s metamorphosis into a vampire is shown as a downfall of her ideal femininity. At first, she was described as an ideal woman, gentle, beautiful and passive. But when she becomes a vampire, she is described as predatory, sexual and “other”. Van Helsing and his group of men are horrified by her and destroy her violently, not to save her, but return gender and national order.

Mina Harker is a complete opposite to Lucy, she is an ideal woman, rational, loyal and disciplined. She even served as a mediator between Dracula and the men who were hunting him. Her half vampirization created a link between her and Dracula and the men seize the opportunity to destroy the monster. She is a perfect example of a woman who sacrifices herself for the men’s benefit.

The contrast between the vampire women of Transylvania and the English women in the novel is also significant. The three vampire women in *Castle Dracula* or as they called: Dracula’s “brides” are described in explicitly sexual and dangerous terms not matching English prototypes of how women should look and behave. They are beautiful and yet deadly, seductive and predatory. They represent the unrestrained female sexuality of the East in contrast to control domestic English womanhood.

The xenophobic elements in *Dracula* can be observed through the male characters of the novel. All the men are white and racially the same despite different nations, they are English, American and Dutch, but all are white, Christian and male. Their collective hostility against Dracula can be an allegory for the Western civilization defense versus non-western threatening foreign. However, Van Helsing is a Dutch professor and a foreigner himself, but his identity does not regarded as threatening, because his values interconnect with British ones.

The last important feature of xenophobia in *Dracula* is the way the novel uses language and literacy as markers of civilization. The novel is written using the epistolary narrative, which means that it is structures as a gathering of diaries, letters, newspapers, phonograph recordings and they all are written by English characters and is considered the only authoritative voice of narration.

Dracula himself is very intelligent and educated, but he does not have a voice in the novel. We never read any documentation written by him. He exists only because he was described by someone who presents Dracula from the xenophobic point of view and systematically points out his non-human qualities and strangeness. The narrative exclusion is itself a form of violence: the foreign “other” is denied the right to tell his own story, to explain his perspective or to oppose the version of events presented by his enemies. As many scholars state, the novel *Dracula* is deeply connected with modern technologies like typewriters and phonographs, which are used by the privileged white European people, while Count Dracula does not have access to it and uses ancient powers. This comparison of modern West and ancient East emphasizes novel’s xenophobic features.

Van Helsing’s voice in the novel is another aspect of the novel’s ideology. As a Dutch speaker of English, he speaks with German accent and uses idioms borrowed from the German language. Van Helsing is also a representation of the foreign “other”, but he is not shown as threat to English society, on the contrary he is treated with respect and admiration. He is considered charming, rather than threatening, because he is a hero and serves for the good of England. He does not have traits of invasion like Dracula does, that’s why he is considered safe.

Jonathan Harker’s early founding of the Transylvanian nation and customs are considered as ethnographic descriptions, where Jonathan explores an exotic and inferior culture. Mary Louise Pratt in her “Imperial eyes: travel writing and transculturation” claims that such travel writing was never neutral and that it was managed within a colonial power which made everyone think that the West superior and gave it the right to observe the observed. [7]

The novel’s focus on documentation and evidence is connected to Victorian concern with truth, knowledge and rationality. The heroes collect their documents into Van Helsing’s memorandum, which is a collective record of Dracula’s presence. This act of making a document is fundamentally

Western activity, which is rational, systematic and oriented toward legal and scientific standards of evidence. It acts as a huge contrast to the oral tradition of East European folklore. Even though the Eastern Europeans were right in their superstitions about vampires, the novel reframes this knowledge in favor of English superiority.

In conclusion, Bram Stoker's *Dracula* is a rich novel whose horror elements are inseparable from Victorian England's politics. The novel constructs its central threat, Count Dracula, as a figure of racial and cultural "otherness", whose invasion of England encodes a wide range of Victorian anxieties: about immigration, decline of British Empire, boundaries between East and West, gender roles and female sexuality.

Through an analysis of Dracula's appearance and race, the location of Transylvania, the narrative and its resonance with reverse colonization, the intersection with xenophobia with gender politics, and politics of language, it was shown that the novel's xenophobia is not accidental or shallow, but structural and organized. It shapes the plot, the characters, the narrative style, and the ideology of the story. The defeat of Dracula is not a simple conquer of a monster, it is reinforcement of white, western, Christian civilization over the threatening forces of racial and cultural difference.

Understanding the historical and ideological depth of Dracula's xenophobia makes it a richer and more significant text. It allows us to see how literature participates in the construction of cultural anxieties and how narratives about monsters are often also narratives about real human fears and conflicts.

Reading *Dracula* today, in a world still marked by xenophobia, nativism and anxiety about immigration, is a reminder of how deeply literature can reflect and shape the prejudices of its time and how significant it is to read these texts critically, with attention to who and how are they represented and whose perspective is taken for granted as the only authority. The foreign "other" of Dracula is not simply a fictional vampire, he is the product of a specific cultural moment and understanding him helps us understand both Victorian Britain and the persistence of xenophobic cognition that is still present in the modern world.

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